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Direct Infusion Workflow

Overall study design

Title of the study	The molecular mechanism of on-demand sterol biosynthesis at organelle contact sites-3		
Document creation date	10/20/2025	Principal investigator	Britta Brügger / Heidelberg Lipidomics
Institution	Heidelberg University Biochemistry Center	Corresponding Email	britta.bruegger@bzh.uni-heidelberg.de
Is the workflow targeted or untargeted?	Targeted	Clinical	No

Lipid extraction

Extraction method	2-phase system	pH adjustment	Hydrochloric acid
2-phase system	Bligh&Dyer	Were internal standards added prior extraction?	Yes

Analytical platform

Ionization additives	Ammonium acetate	Detector	Mass spectrometer
MS type	QTrap	MS vendor	SCIEX
Direct type	Chip	MS Level	MS ²
Mass window for precursor ion isolation (in Da total isolation window)	1	Mass resolution for detected ion at MS ²	Low resolution
Resolution at MS ²	Unit	Recording mode of raw data at MS ²	Profile mode
Was/Were additional dimension/techniques used	No		

Quality control

Blanks	Yes	Type of Blanks	Extraction blank, Solvent blank, Internal standard blank
Quality control	Yes	Type of QC sample	Sample pool

Method qualification and validation

Method validation	Yes	Lipid recovery	Yes
Dynamic quantification range	No	Limit of quantitation (LOQ)/Limit of detection (LOD)	No
Precision	Yes	Accuracy	Yes
Guidelines followed	None		

Reporting

Are reported raw data uploaded into repository?	Available on request	Are metadata available?	Available on request
Raw data upload	Available on request	Additional comments	Raw data will be uploaded to MetaboLights

Sample Descriptions

Control RNAi/BAP31 RNAi/Contro plasmid/OE BAP31 / Human / Cells

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Provided preanalytical information	Time to freeze, Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles, Preservation method
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Instant sample preparation	No
Time to freeze	between 10 and 620 min	Snap freezing in liquid N2	Yes
Storage temperature	-80 °C	Storage time (month)	0
Freeze-thaw cycles	1	Additives	None
Were samples stored under inert gas?	No	Additional preservation methods	No
Biobank samples	No		

Lipid Class Descriptions

1) ST[M]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	ST	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	Molecular species level	MS ² adduct	[M] ⁺
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
-FA2:0(+HO)-Cholesterol(35)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ² verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ²	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Limit of detection	No	Lipid Identification Software	Lipidview 1.3
Data manipulation	Background subtraction	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Nomenclature for fragment ions	No	Further identification remarks	Derivatization of sterols with acetyl chloride to sterol acetate.

1) ST[M]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ²
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ²			
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
d7-ST27:1;O	-FA2:0(+HO)-d7-Cholesterol(35)		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	One factor for all species
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	LipidView 1.3 and homemade
Batch correction	No		